

UNDERSTANDING BASIC LINGUOCULTURAL CONCEPTS IN THE ENGLISH PICTURE OF THE WORLD

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Annotation: This thesis examines the fundamental linguocultural aspects embedded within the English language, investigating how linguistic structures, idiomatic expressions, and cultural references collectively shape the worldview of English speakers. Language is not merely a tool for communication; it serves as a reflection of the culture from which it emerges. Understanding the English language thus entails delving into the cultural, historical, and social contexts that inform its development and usage. Drawing on the ideas of notable philosophers and linguists, this study will elucidate how language encapsulates and conveys the essence of cultural identity, social values, and collective experience.

Key words: linguoculture, language, cultural attitudes, understanding of existence, language picture of the world, linguocultural competence, global understanding.

To begin, the thesis will explore the concept of linguocultural competence, which involves an awareness of how language functions within cultural contexts. Philosophers such as Ludwig Wittgenstein argued that "the limits of my language mean the limits of my world," highlighting the intrinsic connection between language and perception. This thesis will analyze specific linguistic features—such as vocabulary, syntax, and pragmatics—that are influenced by cultural norms and values. For instance, the use of politeness strategies in English varies depending on social hierarchies and situational contexts, reflecting broader cultural attitudes toward respect and communication. By examining these features, we can better understand how English speakers navigate social interactions and convey meaning within their cultural framework. Next, the thesis will delve into idiomatic expressions, which often carry meanings rooted in cultural contexts that may be unfamiliar to non-native speakers. Phrases such as "kick the bucket" or "break the ice" reflect historical or social realities. The study will draw on the ideas of Martin Heidegger, who emphasized the notion of "being-in-the-world" and how language shapes our understanding of existence. By analyzing idiomatic expressions, we can uncover

the cultural practices and beliefs that inform the English-speaking experience. Understanding these expressions can illuminate the underlying values and experiences that shape the English-speaking world, revealing how language acts as a repository of cultural knowledge.

Cultural references in English—ranging from literature and folklore to contemporary media—will also be a significant focus of this thesis. Philosophers like Mikhail Bakhtin argued for the idea of dialogism, which posits that meaning is created through the interaction of diverse voices and perspectives. English literature, including works by authors such as Shakespeare and contemporary writers, serves as a medium through which cultural narratives are conveyed. This thesis will analyze specific texts and cultural artifacts, highlighting how they embody and disseminate the cultural narratives that inform the English language picture of the world.

Furthermore, the thesis will explore the impact of globalization and technological advancements on the English language and its associated culture. As English continues to evolve, influenced by various cultures and languages, it becomes a dynamic medium for cross-cultural communication. Drawing on the ideas of post-structuralists like Jacques Derrida, who emphasized the fluidity of meaning, this section will consider how the proliferation of English as a global lingua franca alters traditional linguistic and cultural paradigms. The study will address the implications of these changes for identity and cultural preservation, as well as the challenges and opportunities presented by a rapidly changing linguistic landscape.

Additionally, this thesis will incorporate the perspective of philosopher Edward Sapir, who asserted that language is a key factor in shaping thought. Sapir's theory of linguistic relativity suggests that the structure of a language influences its speakers' worldview. This section will explore how the linguistic characteristics of English, such as its emphasis on individualism and directness, reflect and reinforce specific cultural values.

Finally, the thesis will argue that understanding the basic linguocultural aspects of the English language is essential for fostering intercultural communication and promoting global understanding. As English speakers increasingly engage with diverse cultures, the ability to recognize and appreciate the cultural nuances embedded in language becomes crucial. Philosopher Kwame Anthony Appiah's concept of "cosmopolitanism" posits that individuals should cultivate an openness to other cultures while maintaining their own identities. This understanding can enhance empathy and cooperation

in an interconnected world, making it imperative for educators and learners to prioritize linguocultural competence in language education.

In conclusion, this thesis will provide a comprehensive exploration of the basic linguocultural aspects that shape the English language picture of the world. By analyzing linguistic features, idiomatic expressions, cultural references, and the impacts of globalization through the lens of philosophical ideas, the study aims to illuminate the complex interplay between language and culture. Ultimately, this research seeks to enhance our understanding of how English not only reflects but also influences the diverse experiences and identities of its speakers, contributing to a richer, more nuanced view of the global linguistic landscape.

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